

Fixed Digits Repetitions Prime Patterns of Length 6¹

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Abstract

The author [7] worked with patterns in prime numbers in such a way that they can be extended by inserting digits in repeated ways, and still remains prime numbers. These types of prime numbers are called **fixed digits repetitions prime patterns**. In this work, **multiple choice prime patterns** are considered. Multiple choice means that the pattern formed by same prime number can be represented by more than one way. The work is for **prime patterns** of length 6. When we talk of length 6, it means that the pattern at length 7 is no more a prime number. A complete list of prime patterns with possible number of digits repetitions is written in reduced form. This work is a revised and enlarged version of author's previous three works [7, 10, 11] done in 2017. Similar kind of work on lengths 10, 9, 8 and 7 can seen in [14, 15].

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¹It is reorganized and enlarged version of author's previous works: <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a17.pdf>, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a93.pdf> and <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a94.pdf> done in 2017.

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1 Introduction

First let us understand what we mean by “**patterns in prime numbers**”. It is understood as repetition of same digits in limited continuous way the resulting number still remains as prime numbers. See some examples,

- 71
701
7001
70001
700001.
- 11
116141
1161416141
11614161416141
116141614161416141.

Let us analyse the above prime numbers. In the first case digit 0 repeats 4 times. In the second case the the digit 1614 repeats 4 times. Also to note that in each case the next number in the string are not prime numbers. See below:

$$700001 = 197 \times 35533;$$
$$11614161416141614161416141 = 82549 \times 14069415033666809.$$

Below is an another example of a prime number 2473, where the pattern of length 7 is formed in three different ways:

- ▶ 24 73
24 73572 73
24 73572 73572 73
24 73572 73572 73572 73
24 73572 73572 73572 73572 73
24 73572 73572 73572 73572 73572 73.
- ▶ 247 3
247 35727 3
247 35727 35727 3
247 35727 35727 35727 3
247 35727 35727 35727 35727 3
247 35727 35727 35727 35727 35727 3.
- ▶ 2473
2473 57273
2473 57273 57273
2473 57273 57273 57273
2473 57273 57273 57273 57273
2473 57273 57273 57273 57273 57273.

We observe that in all the 3 cases the primes are the same in each line, for example, the last one in each case is

2473572735727357273572735727357273.

The difference is only in repetition of digits, 73572, 35727 and 57273 respectively. But it doesn't happens always. There are patterns with same prime number but the pattern are formed by different primes. See below the example:

▶ **168171**

249 **168171**
249 249 **168171**
249 249 249 **168171**
249 249 249 249 **168171**
249 249 249 249 249 **168171**
249 249 249 249 249 **168171**.

▶ **168171**

16 117 **8171**
16 117 117 **8171**
16 117 117 117 **8171**
16 117 117 117 117 **8171**
16 117 117 117 117 117 **8171**
16 117 117 117 117 117 **8171**.

From above we observe that the starting prime number in each case is 168171, but the chance comes from the second line onwards. Here we have next six primes are different in each case. For simplicity, let us call the patterns (1) or (2) as "**multiple patterns in prime number**". A general study of this kind of patterns in prime numbers refer author's work [7]. Here our aim is to give **multiple patterns in prime numbers of length 6**. Results for lengths 10, 9, 8 and 7 are discussed in [8, 14, 15]. In the end a complete list of up to 5-digits repetitions is also given in reduced form, separated according to number of repetitions of digits.

The idea this work is from the work appeared in [3]. For more work on numbers see the references [1, 2, 4, 5]. For summary of auhtor's work on numbers refer [6, 12, 13].

2 Multiple Choice Prime Patterns of Length 6

This section brings multiple choice prime patterns of length 6. There are much more possibilities, but we have given only three in each case, starting from 14-tuples to double choice. In cases of 14 and 13-tuples, three is only one possibility in each case.

2.1 14-tuple Choice Prime Patterns

▶ **5009**

112743 **5009**
112743 112743 **5009**
112743 112743 112743 **5009**
112743 112743 112743 112743 **5009**
112743 112743 112743 112743 112743 **5009**.

▶ **5009**

597807 **5009**
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597807 597807 597807 **5009**
597807 597807 597807 597807 **5009**
597807 597807 597807 597807 597807 **5009**.

▶ **5009**

5 39 **009**
5 39 39 **009**
5 39 39 39 **009**
5 39 39 39 39 **009**
5 39 39 39 39 39 **009**.

- ▶ 5009
5 833742 009
5 833742 833742 009
5 833742 833742 833742 009
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5 833742 833742 833742 833742 833742 009.
- ▶ 5009
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- ▶ 5009
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- ▶ 5009
5 899811 009
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5 899811 899811 899811 009
5 899811 899811 899811 899811 009
5 899811 899811 899811 899811 899811 009.
- ▶ 5009
500 30966 9
500 30966 30966 9
500 30966 30966 30966 9
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- ▶ 5009
500 948129 9
500 948129 948129 9
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- ▶ 5009
5 978075 009
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5 978075 978075 978075 009
5 978075 978075 978075 978075 009
5 978075 978075 978075 978075 978075 009.
- ▶ 5009
500 37350 9
500 37350 37350 9
500 37350 37350 37350 9
500 37350 37350 37350 37350 9
500 37350 37350 37350 37350 37350 9.
- ▶ 5009
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- ▶ 5009
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- ▶ 5009
5009 728277
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2.2 13-tuple Choice Prime Patterns

- ▶ 1621
31308 1621
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- ▶ 1621
495411 1621
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- ▶ 1621
755889 1621
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- ▶ 1621
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- ▶ 1621
874602 1621
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874602 874602 874602 874602 874602 1621.

- ▶ **1621**
1 623766 **621**
1 623766 623766 **621**
1 623766 623766 623766 **621**
1 623766 623766 623766 623766 **621**
1 623766 623766 623766 623766 623766 **621**.
- ▶ **1621**
16 431676 **21**
16 431676 431676 **21**
16 431676 431676 431676 **21**
16 431676 431676 431676 431676 **21**
16 431676 431676 431676 431676 431676 **21**.
- ▶ **1621**
162 376662 **1**
162 376662 376662 **1**
162 376662 376662 376662 **1**
162 376662 376662 376662 376662 **1**
162 376662 376662 376662 376662 376662 **1**.
- ▶ **1621**
162 693315 **1**
162 693315 693315 **1**
162 693315 693315 693315 **1**
162 693315 693315 693315 693315 **1**
162 693315 693315 693315 693315 693315 **1**.
- ▶ **1621**
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1621 894723 894723
1621 894723 894723 894723
1621 894723 894723 894723 894723
1621 894723 894723 894723 894723 894723.

2.3 12-tuple Choice Prime Patterns

- ▶ **691**
820365 **691**
820365 820365 **691**
820365 820365 820365 **691**
820365 820365 820365 820365 **691**
820365 820365 820365 820365 820365 **691**.
- ▶ **691**
6 537900 **91**
6 537900 537900 **91**
6 537900 537900 537900 **91**
6 537900 537900 537900 537900 **91**
6 537900 537900 537900 537900 537900 **91**.
- ▶ **691**
69 134736 **1**
69 134736 134736 **1**
69 134736 134736 134736 **1**
69 134736 134736 134736 134736 **1**
69 134736 134736 134736 134736 134736 **1**.
- ▶ **691**
908931 **691**
908931 908931 **691**
908931 908931 908931 **691**
908931 908931 908931 908931 **691**
908931 908931 908931 908931 908931 **691**.
- ▶ **691**
69 1416 **1**
69 1416 1416 **1**
69 1416 1416 1416 **1**
69 1416 1416 1416 1416 **1**
69 1416 1416 1416 1416 1416 **1**.
- ▶ **691**
69 302523 **1**
69 302523 302523 **1**
69 302523 302523 302523 **1**
69 302523 302523 302523 302523 **1**
69 302523 302523 302523 302523 302523 **1**.
- ▶ **691**
6 126945 **91**
6 126945 126945 **91**
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6 126945 126945 126945 126945 126945 **91**.
- ▶ **691**
69 1722 **1**
69 1722 1722 **1**
69 1722 1722 1722 **1**
69 1722 1722 1722 1722 **1**
69 1722 1722 1722 1722 1722 **1**.
- ▶ **691**
691 4161
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- ▶ 2243
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2 198828 198828 243
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- ▶ 2243
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- ▶ 2243
2 580713 243
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- ▶ 2243
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- ▶ 4057
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- ▶ 691
691 253113
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- ▶ 2243
22 480639 43
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- ▶ 2243
22 498027 43
22 498027 498027 43
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- ▶ 2243
22 735126 43
22 735126 735126 43
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- ▶ 2243
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40 732636 57
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405 7437 7
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2.4 11-tuple Choice Prime Patterns

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| <p>▶ 11
200517 11
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1 2256 1
1 2256 2256 1
1 2256 2256 2256 1
1 2256 2256 2256 2256 1
1 2256 2256 2256 2256 2256 1.</p> | <p>▶ 11
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1 147231 1
1 147231 147231 1
1 147231 147231 147231 1
1 147231 147231 147231 147231 1
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1 36 1
1 36 36 1
1 36 36 36 1
1 36 36 36 36 1
1 36 36 36 36 36 1.</p> | <p>▶ 11
1 159312 1
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1 335769 3
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757 7923
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- ▶ 757
757 9471
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757 528753
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2.5 10-tuple Choice Prime Patterns

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1 407184 07
1 407184 407184 07
1 407184 407184 407184 07
1 407184 407184 407184 407184 07
1 407184 407184 407184 407184 407184 07.
- ▶ 107
10 66108 7
10 66108 66108 7
10 66108 66108 66108 7
10 66108 66108 66108 66108 7
10 66108 66108 66108 66108 66108 7.
- ▶ 107
10 197358 7
10 197358 197358 7
10 197358 197358 197358 7
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10 197358 197358 197358 197358 197358 7.
- ▶ 107
1 665568 07
1 665568 665568 07
1 665568 665568 665568 07
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- ▶ 107
10 77541 7
10 77541 77541 7
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107 99
107 99 99
107 99 99 99
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107 99 99 99 99 99.
- ▶ 107
1 666687 07
1 666687 666687 07
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1 666687 666687 666687 666687 07
1 666687 666687 666687 666687 666687 07.
- ▶ 107
10 88377 7
10 88377 88377 7
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- ▶ 1637
16 200280 37
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- ▶ 1637
16 779667 37
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16 559317 37
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16 871941 37
16 871941 871941 37
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163 669669 7
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2 48876 297
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22 467124 97
22 467124 467124 97
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2 323253 297
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22 589467 97
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22 589467 589467 589467 589467 589467 97.
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2 10173 297
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22 188874 97
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229 59430 7
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2.6 9-tuple Choice Prime Patterns

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2 8733 3
2 8733 8733 3
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2 303492 3
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2 51195 3
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2 82443 3
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23 222621
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591690 79
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7 39585 9
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75954 79
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7 8793 9
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7 59547 9
7 59547 59547 9
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| <p>▶ 79
7 260214 9
7 260214 260214 9
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7 429114 9
7 429114 429114 9
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7 429114 429114 429114 429114 9
7 429114 429114 429114 429114 429114 9.</p> | <p>▶ 79
7 649740 9
7 649740 649740 9
7 649740 649740 649740 9
7 649740 649740 649740 649740 9
7 649740 649740 649740 649740 649740 9.</p> |
| <p>▶ 127
87948 127
87948 87948 127
87948 87948 87948 127
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87948 87948 87948 87948 87948 127.</p> | <p>▶ 127
1 808770 27
1 808770 808770 27
1 808770 808770 808770 27
1 808770 808770 808770 808770 27
1 808770 808770 808770 808770 808770 27.</p> | <p>▶ 127
12 956184 7
12 956184 956184 7
12 956184 956184 956184 7
12 956184 956184 956184 956184 7
12 956184 956184 956184 956184 956184 7.</p> |
| <p>▶ 127
1 576 27
1 576 576 27
1 576 576 576 27
1 576 576 576 576 27
1 576 576 576 576 576 27.</p> | <p>▶ 127
12 765 7
12 765 765 7
12 765 765 765 7
12 765 765 765 765 7
12 765 765 765 765 765 7.</p> | <p>▶ 127
127 657
127 657 657
127 657 657 657
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127 657 657 657 657 657.</p> |
| <p>▶ 127
1 51126 27
1 51126 51126 27
1 51126 51126 51126 27
1 51126 51126 51126 51126 27
1 51126 51126 51126 51126 51126 27.</p> | <p>▶ 127
12 878904 7
12 878904 878904 7
12 878904 878904 878904 7
12 878904 878904 878904 878904 7
12 878904 878904 878904 878904 878904 7.</p> | <p>▶ 127
127 689571
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127 689571 689571 689571 689571 689571.</p> |

2.7 8-tuple Choice Prime Patterns

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|--|---|---|
| <p>▶ 467
248376 467
248376 248376 467
248376 248376 248376 467
248376 248376 248376 248376 467
248376 248376 248376 248376 248376 467.</p> | <p>▶ 467
4 895419 67
4 895419 895419 67
4 895419 895419 895419 67
4 895419 895419 895419 895419 67
4 895419 895419 895419 895419 895419 67.</p> | <p>▶ 467
46 62769 7
46 62769 62769 7
46 62769 62769 62769 7
46 62769 62769 62769 62769 7
46 62769 62769 62769 62769 62769 7.</p> |
| <p>▶ 467
315051 467
315051 315051 467
315051 315051 315051 467
315051 315051 315051 315051 467
315051 315051 315051 315051 315051 467.</p> | <p>▶ 467
4 922578 67
4 922578 922578 67
4 922578 922578 922578 67
4 922578 922578 922578 922578 67
4 922578 922578 922578 922578 922578 67.</p> | <p>▶ 467
46 627099 7
46 627099 627099 7
46 627099 627099 627099 7
46 627099 627099 627099 627099 7
46 627099 627099 627099 627099 627099 7.</p> |

- ▶ 467
46 758835 7
46 758835 758835 7
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- ▶ 601
131034 601
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- ▶ 601
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- ▶ 601
609876 601
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- ▶ 751
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- ▶ 751
7 1338 51
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- ▶ 467
467 588357
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- ▶ 601
961983 601
961983 961983 601
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961983 961983 961983 961983 961983 601.
- ▶ 601
60 607026 1
60 607026 607026 1
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- ▶ 601
60 987660 1
60 987660 987660 1
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- ▶ 751
7 100947 51
7 100947 100947 51
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- ▶ 751
75 394149 1
75 394149 394149 1
75 394149 394149 394149 1
75 394149 394149 394149 394149 1
75 394149 394149 394149 394149 394149 1.
- ▶ 751
75 729834 1
75 729834 729834 1
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- ▶ 601
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- ▶ 601
601 405873
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- ▶ 751
75 887187 1
75 887187 887187 1
75 887187 887187 887187 1
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- ▶ 751
751 282177
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2.8 7-tuple Choice Prime Patterns

- ▶ 229
 - 2 145320 29
 - 2 145320 145320 29
 - 2 145320 145320 145320 29
 - 2 145320 145320 145320 145320 29
 - 2 145320 145320 145320 145320 145320 29.
- ▶ 229
 - 2 211596 29
 - 2 211596 211596 29
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- ▶ 229
 - 2 276891 29
 - 2 276891 276891 29
 - 2 276891 276891 276891 29
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- ▶ 283
 - 299271 283
 - 299271 299271 283
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 - 2 438816 83
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- ▶ 283
 - 2 992712 83
 - 2 992712 992712 83
 - 2 992712 992712 992712 83
 - 2 992712 992712 992712 992712 83
 - 2 992712 992712 992712 992712 992712 83.
- ▶ 367
 - 3 1188 67
 - 3 1188 1188 67
 - 3 1188 1188 1188 67
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 - 3 1188 1188 1188 1188 1188 67.
- ▶ 229
 - 22 8103 9
 - 22 8103 8103 9
 - 22 8103 8103 8103 9
 - 22 8103 8103 8103 8103 9
 - 22 8103 8103 8103 8103 8103 9.
- ▶ 229
 - 22 115962 9
 - 22 115962 115962 9
 - 22 115962 115962 115962 9
 - 22 115962 115962 115962 115962 9
 - 22 115962 115962 115962 115962 115962 9.
- ▶ 229
 - 22 443286 9
 - 22 443286 443286 9
 - 22 443286 443286 443286 9
 - 22 443286 443286 443286 443286 9
 - 22 443286 443286 443286 443286 443286 9.
- ▶ 283
 - 28 6834 3
 - 28 6834 6834 3
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- ▶ 283
 - 28 67050 3
 - 28 67050 67050 3
 - 28 67050 67050 67050 3
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 - 28 67050 67050 67050 67050 67050 3.
- ▶ 283
 - 283 794829
 - 283 794829 794829
 - 283 794829 794829 794829
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- ▶ 367
 - 3 717057 67
 - 3 717057 717057 67
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 - 3 717057 717057 717057 717057 717057 67.
- ▶ 367
 - 3 870786 67
 - 3 870786 870786 67
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36 75330 7
36 75330 75330 7
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367 53307
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36 445761 7
36 445761 445761 7
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367 775131
367 775131 775131
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367 775131 775131 775131 775131
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2.9 6-tuple Choice Prime Patterns

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335262 7
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844911 7
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727149 7
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3711 233
3711 3711 233
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2 581154 33
2 581154 581154 33
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23 565845 3
23 565845 565845 3
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2 904338 33
2 904338 904338 33
2 904338 904338 904338 33
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2 904338 904338 904338 904338 33.

▶ 233
233 159357
233 159357 159357
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233 159357 159357 159357 159357.

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| <p>▶ 263
5784 263
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842835 263
842835 842835 263
842835 842835 842835 263
842835 842835 842835 842835 263
842835 842835 842835 842835 263.</p> | <p>▶ 263
26 59235 3
26 59235 59235 3
26 59235 59235 59235 3
26 59235 59235 59235 59235 3
26 59235 59235 59235 59235 59235 3.</p> |
| <p>▶ 263
42231 263
42231 42231 263
42231 42231 42231 263
42231 42231 42231 42231 263
42231 42231 42231 42231 263.</p> | <p>▶ 263
2 58611 63
2 58611 58611 63
2 58611 58611 58611 63
2 58611 58611 58611 58611 63
2 58611 58611 58611 58611 63.</p> | <p>▶ 263
26 630441 3
26 630441 630441 3
26 630441 630441 630441 3
26 630441 630441 630441 630441 3
26 630441 630441 630441 630441 630441 3.</p> |

2.10 Quintuple Choice Prime Patterns

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|--|---|---|
| <p>▶ 59
611952 59
611952 611952 59
611952 611952 611952 59
611952 611952 611952 611952 59
611952 611952 611952 611952 611952 59.</p> | <p>▶ 59
5 8313 9
5 8313 8313 9
5 8313 8313 8313 9
5 8313 8313 8313 8313 9
5 8313 8313 8313 8313 8313 9.</p> | <p>▶ 59
59 955881
59 955881 955881
59 955881 955881 955881
59 955881 955881 955881 955881
59 955881 955881 955881 955881 955881.</p> |
| <p>▶ 59
5 3234 9
5 3234 3234 9
5 3234 3234 3234 9
5 3234 3234 3234 3234 9
5 3234 3234 3234 3234 3234 9.</p> | <p>▶ 59
59 83127
59 83127 83127
59 83127 83127 83127
59 83127 83127 83127 83127
59 83127 83127 83127 83127 83127.</p> | |
| <p>▶ 61
3372 61
3372 3372 61
3372 3372 3372 61
3372 3372 3372 3372 61
3372 3372 3372 3372 3372 61.</p> | <p>▶ 61
6 230055 1
6 230055 230055 1
6 230055 230055 230055 1
6 230055 230055 230055 230055 1
6 230055 230055 230055 230055 230055 1.</p> | <p>▶ 61
6 831303 1
6 831303 831303 1
6 831303 831303 831303 1
6 831303 831303 831303 831303 1
6 831303 831303 831303 831303 831303 1.</p> |
| <p>▶ 61
31794 61
31794 31794 61
31794 31794 31794 61
31794 31794 31794 31794 61
31794 31794 31794 31794 31794 61.</p> | <p>▶ 61
6 492783 1
6 492783 492783 1
6 492783 492783 492783 1
6 492783 492783 492783 492783 1
6 492783 492783 492783 492783 492783 1.</p> | |

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|--|---|---|
| <p>▶ 103
1 62040 03
1 62040 62040 03
1 62040 62040 62040 03
1 62040 62040 62040 62040 03
1 62040 62040 62040 62040 62040 03.</p> | <p>▶ 103
10 275769 3
10 275769 275769 3
10 275769 275769 275769 3
10 275769 275769 275769 275769 3
10 275769 275769 275769 275769 275769 3.</p> | <p>▶ 103
10 754047 3
10 754047 754047 3
10 754047 754047 754047 3
10 754047 754047 754047 754047 3
10 754047 754047 754047 754047 754047 3.</p> |
| <p>▶ 103
10 9789 3
10 9789 9789 3
10 9789 9789 9789 3
10 9789 9789 9789 9789 3
10 9789 9789 9789 9789 9789 3.</p> | <p>▶ 103
10 731301 3
10 731301 731301 3
10 731301 731301 731301 3
10 731301 731301 731301 731301 3
10 731301 731301 731301 731301 731301 3.</p> | |

2.11 Quadruple Choice Prime Patterns

- | | |
|--|---|
| <p>▶ 17
191373 17
191373 191373 17
191373 191373 191373 17
191373 191373 191373 191373 17
191373 191373 191373 191373 191373 17.</p> | <p>▶ 17
1 913731 7
1 913731 913731 7
1 913731 913731 913731 7
1 913731 913731 913731 913731 7
1 913731 913731 913731 913731 913731 7.</p> |
| <p>▶ 17
1 28353 7
1 28353 28353 7
1 28353 28353 28353 7
1 28353 28353 28353 28353 7
1 28353 28353 28353 28353 28353 7.</p> | <p>▶ 17
17 133371
17 133371 133371
17 133371 133371 133371
17 133371 133371 133371 133371
17 133371 133371 133371 133371.</p> |
| <p>▶ 37
513045 37
513045 513045 37
513045 513045 513045 37
513045 513045 513045 513045 37
513045 513045 513045 513045 513045 37.</p> | <p>▶ 37
752808 37
752808 752808 37
752808 752808 752808 37
752808 752808 752808 752808 37
752808 752808 752808 752808 752808 37.</p> |
| <p>▶ 37
559287 37
559287 559287 37
559287 559287 559287 37
559287 559287 559287 559287 37
559287 559287 559287 559287 559287 37.</p> | <p>▶ 37
3 405 7
3 405 405 7
3 405 405 405 7
3 405 405 405 405 7
3 405 405 405 405 405 7.</p> |

▶ 47
187887 47
187887 187887 47
187887 187887 187887 47
187887 187887 187887 187887 47
187887 187887 187887 187887 187887 47.

▶ 47
4 41076 7
4 41076 41076 7
4 41076 41076 41076 7
4 41076 41076 41076 41076 7
4 41076 41076 41076 41076 41076 7.

▶ 47
4 135 7
4 135 135 7
4 135 135 135 7
4 135 135 135 135 7
4 135 135 135 135 135 7.

▶ 47
47 3861
47 3861 3861
47 3861 3861 3861
47 3861 3861 3861 3861
47 3861 3861 3861 3861 3861.

2.12 Triple Choice Prime Patterns

▶ 97
44100 97
44100 44100 97
44100 44100 44100 97
44100 44100 44100 44100 97
44100 44100 44100 44100 44100 97.

▶ 97
9 88431 7
9 88431 88431 7
9 88431 88431 88431 7
9 88431 88431 88431 88431 7
9 88431 88431 88431 88431 88431 7.

▶ 97
97 81
97 81 81
97 81 81 81
97 81 81 81 81
97 81 81 81 81 81.

▶ 113
1 270099 13
1 270099 270099 13
1 270099 270099 270099 13
1 270099 270099 270099 270099 13
1 270099 270099 270099 270099 270099 13.

▶ 113
1 858078 13
1 858078 858078 13
1 858078 858078 858078 13
1 858078 858078 858078 858078 13
1 858078 858078 858078 858078 858078 13.

▶ 113
11 842952 3
11 842952 842952 3
11 842952 842952 842952 3
11 842952 842952 842952 842952 3
11 842952 842952 842952 842952 842952 3.

▶ 163
360 163
360 360 163
360 360 360 163
360 360 360 360 163
360 360 360 360 163.

▶ 163
1 81438 63
1 81438 81438 63
1 81438 81438 81438 63
1 81438 81438 81438 81438 63
1 81438 81438 81438 81438 81438 63.

▶ 163
163 47481
163 47481 47481
163 47481 47481 47481
163 47481 47481 47481 47481
163 47481 47481 47481 47481 47481.

2.13 Double Choice Prime Patterns

► 41

4 16119 1
4 16119 16119 1
4 16119 16119 16119 1
4 16119 16119 16119 16119 1
4 16119 16119 16119 16119 16119 1.

► 43

613953 43
613953 613953 43
613953 613953 613953 43
613953 613953 613953 613953 43
613953 613953 613953 613953 613953 43.

► 53

5 88278 3
5 88278 88278 3
5 88278 88278 88278 3
5 88278 88278 88278 88278 3
5 88278 88278 88278 88278 88278 3.

► 41

41 61191
41 61191 61191
41 61191 61191 61191
41 61191 61191 61191 61191
41 61191 61191 61191 61191 61191.

► 43

959574 43
959574 959574 43
959574 959574 959574 43
959574 959574 959574 959574 43
959574 959574 959574 959574 959574 43.

► 53

53 810429
53 810429 810429
53 810429 810429 810429
53 810429 810429 810429 810429
53 810429 810429 810429 810429 810429.

3 Digit-Wise List

Below is a complete list of **prime patterns** of length 6 written in reduced form. It is divided according the repetition of digits. The notations are understood, as given in following two examples:

• [4651, 4(33)651; 6] $\implies$ ► 4 651
4 33 651
4 33 33 651
4 33 33 33 651
4 33 33 33 33 651
4 33 33 33 33 33 651.

• [433, 4(865011)33; 6] $\implies$ ► 4 33
4 865011 33
4 865011 865011 33
4 865011 865011 865011 33
4 865011 865011 865011 865011 33
4 865011 865011 865011 865011 865011 33.

3.1 Single Digit Repetition Pattern

- [13; 13(9); 6]
- [293; 293(9); 6]
- [331; (3)331; 6]
- [331; 3(3)31; 6]
- [331; 33(3)1; 6]
- [367; 36(0)7; 6]
- [617; 6(3)17; 6]
- [887; 88(6)7; 6]
- [919; 9(3)19; 6]
- [5639; 56(0)39; 6]
- [5843; (6)5843; 6]
- [6089; 608(9)9; 6]
- [6089; 6089(9); 6]
- [7283; 728(9)3; 6]
- [7333; 7(6)333; 6]
- [9931; 9(0)931; 6]
- [10061; 10061(3); 6]
- [10531; 105(0)31; 6]
- [10973; 109(6)73; 6]
- [11699; 1169(6)9; 6]
- [11897; (3)11897; 6]
- [12823; 12823(9); 6]
- [16943; 1(3)6943; 6]
- [17599; 1(9)7599; 6]
- [19427; 1(6)9427; 6]
- [22303; 2(3)2303; 6]
- [24623; 24(0)623; 6]
- [25747; 2574(0)7; 6]
- [25847; 2584(0)7; 6]
- [25997; 2(3)5997; 6]
- [26017; 2(9)6017; 6]
- [26189; 261(3)89; 6]
- [26879; 268(9)79; 6]
- [27431; 27(9)431; 6]
- [28069; 28(0)069; 6]
- [28069; 280(0)69; 6]
- [28753; 28(6)753; 6]
- [34369; 34(9)369; 6]
- [34549; (3)34549; 6]
- [34549; 3(3)4549; 6]
- [34841; 3484(3)1; 6]
- [35507; 355(0)07; 6]
- [35507; 3550(0)7; 6]
- [41201; 41(9)201; 6]
- [42071; (6)42071; 6]
- [42677; 4267(0)7; 6]
- [42821; 4282(3)1; 6]
- [44893; 44(3)893; 6]
- [48953; 4(6)8953; 6]
- [53527; 5352(0)7; 6]
- [58073; 580(3)73; 6]
- [60727; 607(6)27; 6]
- [62819; 6281(3)9; 6]
- [63299; 63(0)299; 6]
- [64109; 641(9)09; 6]
- [66791; 66(0)791; 6]
- [68597; 685(6)97; 6]
- [69493; 6(9)9493; 6]
- [69493; 69(9)493; 6]
- [73751; 7(3)3751; 6]
- [73751; 73(3)751; 6]
- [76543; 7(6)6543; 6]
- [76543; 76(6)543; 6]
- [76949; 7694(6)9; 6]
- [87257; 8(6)7257; 6]
- [88301; 88(0)301; 6]
- [91573; 9(3)1573; 6]
- [98257; 9(3)8257; 6]
- [98911; 9(0)8911; 6]
- [102161; 1021(9)61; 6]
- [102497; 1024(6)97; 6]
- [104347; 1043(0)47; 6]
- [109621; 109(6)621; 6]
- [109621; 1096(6)21; 6]
- [112349; 11(9)2349; 6]
- [115327; 11(0)5327; 6]
- [117787; (3)117787; 6]
- [121687; 121687(9); 6]
- [122167; (6)122167; 6]
- [126307; 12(0)6307; 6]
- [133069; 13(9)3069; 6]
- [133691; 1336(0)91; 6]
- [133999; 13(9)3999; 6]
- [136027; 13(0)6027; 6]
- [139369; 1393(0)69; 6]
- [143947; 14394(3)7; 6]
- [145861; 145(0)861; 6]
- [149921; 14992(3)1; 6]
- [153607; 15360(3)7; 6]
- [155303; 15530(6)3; 6]
- [155599; 15559(6)9; 6]
- [157247; 1572(6)47; 6]
- [159553; 15(6)9553; 6]
- [160159; 16015(6)9; 6]
- [161093; 16109(3)3; 6]
- [161093; 161093(3); 6]
- [161237; 1(6)61237; 6]
- [161237; 16(6)1237; 6]
- [163561; 16(3)3561; 6]
- [163561; 163(3)561; 6]
- [166949; 1669(0)49; 6]
- [167711; 1(0)67711; 6]
- [168677; 1(0)68677; 6]
- [172259; 172(6)259; 6]
- [174989; (6)174989; 6]
- [175103; 17510(9)3; 6]
- [179021; 179(6)021; 6]
- [183919; 18391(6)9; 6]
- [184993; 184(3)993; 6]
- [187337; 18733(0)7; 6]
- [190699; 19069(6)9; 6]
- [191473; 191(3)473; 6]
- [192037; 192037(9); 6]
- [193763; 19376(0)3; 6]
- [196307; 19630(3)7; 6]
- [198323; 198(3)323; 6]
- [198323; 1983(3)23; 6]
- [200009; 200(3)009; 6]
- [200713; 20071(3)3; 6]
- [200713; 200713(3); 6]
- [202679; 202(0)679; 6]
- [204707; 20470(3)7; 6]
- [205549; 2(9)05549; 6]
- [208673; 20(9)8673; 6]
- [213713; 2137(6)13; 6]
- [215381; 21538(9)1; 6]
- [228203; 2282(3)03; 6]
- [228469; 228(6)469; 6]
- [230353; 23035(9)3; 6]
- [234811; 2(0)34811; 6]
- [238109; 2381(9)09; 6]
- [238759; 23875(6)9; 6]
- [243487; 243487(9); 6]
- [244759; 24475(6)9; 6]
- [256813; 2568(9)13; 6]
- [258887; 2(3)58887; 6]
- [259421; 25(6)9421; 6]
- [264331; 264(3)331; 6]
- [264331; 2643(3)31; 6]
- [264331; 26433(3)1; 6]
- [272737; 27(0)2737; 6]
- [279857; 2(3)79857; 6]
- [283771; 28(6)3771; 6]
- [283861; 2(6)83861; 6]
- [286249; 28624(6)9; 6]
- [286613; 28(0)6613; 6]
- [291419; 291419(3); 6]
- [292441; 29244(3)1; 6]
- [295787; 29578(0)7; 6]
- [296581; 2965(6)81; 6]
- [299389; 29938(6)9; 6]
- [301141; 30(3)1141; 6]
- [301793; 3017(0)93; 6]
- [315811; 31581(3)1; 6]
- [318841; 31884(3)1; 6]
- [322807; 32(6)2807; 6]

- [332567; 3325(0)67; 6]
- [336727; 3367(0)27; 6]
- [337013; (3)337013; 6]
- [337013; 3(3)37013; 6]
- [337013; 33(3)7013; 6]
- [340429; 3404(3)29; 6]
- [341839; 34(6)1839; 6]
- [347587; 34758(0)7; 6]
- [347951; 347(6)951; 6]
- [361223; 36122(9)3; 6]
- [365063; 365(0)063; 6]
- [365063; 3650(0)63; 6]
- [371387; 37138(0)7; 6]
- [377711; 37(3)7711; 6]
- [379679; 37967(9)9; 6]
- [379679; 379679(9); 6]
- [385657; 38565(3)7; 6]
- [386413; 3(9)86413; 6]
- [389437; 3(9)89437; 6]
- [394501; 3(6)94501; 6]
- [394733; 39(6)4733; 6]
- [396601; 396(9)601; 6]
- [402529; 4025(0)29; 6]
- [407137; 40713(0)7; 6]
- [408623; 4086(9)23; 6]
- [409499; 4094(9)99; 6]
- [409499; 40949(9)9; 6]
- [409499; 409499(9); 6]
- [411011; 41101(3)1; 6]
- [423403; 42340(6)3; 6]
- [427381; 42738(3)1; 6]
- [427969; (6)427969; 6]
- [428227; 42(0)8227; 6]
- [431251; 431(6)251; 6]
- [435569; 43556(3)9; 6]
- [440507; 44050(9)7; 6]
- [448633; 44863(0)3; 6]
- [453317; 45(3)3317; 6]
- [453317; 453(3)317; 6]
- [453317; 4533(3)17; 6]
- [455321; 4(0)55321; 6]
- [455737; 45(9)5737; 6]
- [458327; 4(6)58327; 6]
- [460127; 4(3)60127; 6]
- [461693; 461(0)693; 6]
- [471553; 4715(6)53; 6]
- [488441; 48844(3)1; 6]
- [490201; 49(6)0201; 6]
- [494317; 49(6)4317; 6]
- [495953; 4(6)95953; 6]
- [500839; 50083(6)9; 6]
- [511961; 51(3)1961; 6]
- [515153; 515(6)153; 6]
- [515597; 51559(0)7; 6]
- [519391; 5193(0)91; 6]
- [520151; 520(6)151; 6]
- [522211; 5222(0)11; 6]
- [529603; 52(3)9603; 6]
- [530669; 5306(0)69; 6]
- [531331; 53(6)1331; 6]
- [542197; 54219(0)7; 6]
- [545663; 5456(0)63; 6]
- [550181; 5(9)50181; 6]
- [564979; 564979(3); 6]
- [577097; 5770(6)97; 6]
- [595513; 595(0)513; 6]
- [597899; (9)597899; 6]
- [600791; 600791(3); 6]
- [606839; 606839(3); 6]
- [611803; 6118(0)03; 6]
- [611803; 61180(0)3; 6]
- [613609; 61(9)3609; 6]
- [613813; 61381(9)3; 6]
- [617879; 6(9)17879; 6]
- [622177; 62(0)2177; 6]
- [624709; 6247(9)09; 6]
- [625169; 6(3)25169; 6]
- [625213; 62521(6)3; 6]
- [637519; 63751(3)9; 6]
- [637873; 637(0)873; 6]
- [653431; 6(9)53431; 6]
- [653903; 653(0)903; 6]
- [654191; 6(9)54191; 6]
- [655651; 65(3)5651; 6]
- [670409; 6704(9)09; 6]
- [675419; 67(6)5419; 6]
- [679433; 6794(6)33; 6]
- [691289; 6(9)91289; 6]
- [691289; 69(9)1289; 6]
- [691399; 69139(6)9; 6]
- [693079; 693079(3); 6]
- [697951; 697(6)951; 6]
- [698287; 6(9)98287; 6]
- [698287; 69(9)8287; 6]
- [701549; 7015(0)49; 6]
- [706801; 706(9)801; 6]
- [712507; 7(0)12507; 6]
- [712807; 7128(0)07; 6]
- [712807; 71280(0)7; 6]
- [722149; 72(0)2149; 6]
- [723071; 72(3)3071; 6]
- [723071; 723(3)071; 6]
- [734329; 734(0)329; 6]
- [737717; 7377(3)17; 6]
- [738643; 73864(9)3; 6]
- [744301; 74430(9)1; 6]
- [748777; 7(6)48777; 6]
- [753821; 7(9)53821; 6]
- [760901; 76090(3)1; 6]
- [778667; 7786(3)67; 6]
- [779983; 77998(6)3; 6]
- [783361; 7(9)83361; 6]
- [784981; 784(0)981; 6]
- [794509; 7945(9)09; 6]
- [795979; 79(3)5979; 6]
- [797473; 7(0)97473; 6]
- [805267; 805(0)267; 6]
- [810583; 81058(9)3; 6]
- [816227; 8162(0)27; 6]
- [817319; 8(6)17319; 6]
- [819457; 81(0)9457; 6]
- [819487; 819(0)487; 6]
- [823601; 82360(3)1; 6]
- [827987; 82798(3)7; 6]
- [841727; 8(0)41727; 6]
- [847969; (6)847969; 6]
- [849997; 849(3)997; 6]
- [854407; 85(9)4407; 6]
- [856949; 85694(6)9; 6]
- [860257; 86025(0)7; 6]
- [860417; 8604(3)17; 6]
- [874387; 87438(0)7; 6]
- [896633; 89663(0)3; 6]
- [907399; 907(6)399; 6]
- [921589; 9(6)21589; 6]
- [925843; 92(6)5843; 6]
- [931811; 9(3)31811; 6]
- [931811; 93(3)1811; 6]
- [931921; 931(6)921; 6]
- [933923; 93392(9)3; 6]
- [935489; 93548(0)9; 6]
- [935603; 93560(9)3; 6]
- [938879; 938(6)879; 6]
- [941741; 941(9)741; 6]
- [943841; 94(6)3841; 6]
- [946741; (3)946741; 6]
- [947377; 94737(9)7; 6]
- [955709; 95(6)5709; 6]
- [955967; 95(6)5967; 6]
- [965411; 96541(3)1; 6]
- [965851; 965(9)851; 6]
- [967937; 96(3)7937; 6]
- [975313; (6)975313; 6]
- [975797; 9(6)75797; 6]
- [976307; 976(9)307; 6]
- [981637; 98163(0)7; 6]
- [983267; 98(6)3267; 6]
- [989777; 989(3)777; 6]
- [999959; 99(6)9959; 6]

3.2 Two Digits Repetitions

- [11; 1(36)1; 6]
- [11; 1(72)1; 6]
- [97; 97(81); 6]
- [107; 107(99); 6]
- [191; 19(21)1; 6]
- [397; 39(21)7; 6]
- [677; 6(84)77; 6]
- [877; (78)877; 6]
- [1069; 10(18)69; 6]
- [1091; 109(66)1; 6]
- [1459; (42)1459; 6]
- [1583; 1(12)583; 6]
- [1597; 1(66)597; 6]
- [1601; (57)1601; 6]
- [2309; (18)2309; 6]
- [2477; (90)2477; 6]
- [2837; 283(39)7; 6]
- [2957; 2957(69); 6]
- [3181; 3(69)181; 6]
- [3221; 3(99)221; 6]
- [3323; 332(90)3; 6]
- [3571; 3(27)571; 6]
- [3761; 376(81)1; 6]
- [3911; 39(33)11; 6]
- [4651; 4(33)651; 6]
- [4733; 4(48)733; 6]
- [5009; 5(39)009; 6]
- [5119; 511(54)9; 6]
- [5297; 5(60)297; 6]
- [5573; 5(93)573; 6]
- [5741; 57(96)41; 6]
- [6011; 6011(27); 6]
- [6043; 6043(69); 6]
- [6121; 61(63)21; 6]
- [6317; 6(48)317; 6]
- [6373; 6373(69); 6]
- [6679; 667(69)9; 6]
- [6709; (93)6709; 6]
- [6997; 699(96)7; 6]
- [7177; 717(69)7; 6]
- [7583; (69)7583; 6]
- [8191; 81(72)91; 6]
- [8573; 85(78)73; 6]
- [8573; 857(87)3; 6]
- [8699; 86(93)99; 6]
- [8699; 869(39)9; 6]
- [9059; (21)9059; 6]
- [9587; 95(69)87; 6]
- [9613; 96(51)13; 6]
- [10303; 1(96)0303; 6]
- [10433; 1043(87)3; 6]
- [10499; 1(75)0499; 6]
- [10529; (93)10529; 6]
- [10781; 10(60)781; 6]
- [11287; 11(96)287; 6]
- [12049; 12049(81); 6]
- [12391; (54)12391; 6]
- [13441; (15)13441; 6]
- [13441; 1(51)3441; 6]
- [13681; 1(99)3681; 6]
- [14009; (42)14009; 6]
- [14633; 146(51)33; 6]
- [15331; 1(57)5331; 6]
- [15331; 15(75)331; 6]
- [15359; 1(27)5359; 6]
- [15461; 1546(27)1; 6]
- [15649; 1564(99)9; 6]
- [15649; 15649(99); 6]
- [16187; (15)16187; 6]
- [16187; 1(51)6187; 6]
- [16253; 16(48)253; 6]
- [17491; 174(75)91; 6]
- [18719; 1(57)8719; 6]
- [18869; 1(69)8869; 6]
- [19541; (18)19541; 6]
- [19541; 1(27)9541; 6]
- [19541; 1(81)9541; 6]
- [19577; (12)19577; 6]
- [19577; 1(21)9577; 6]
- [20411; 20(93)411; 6]
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3.3 Three Digits Repetitions

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3.4 Four Digits Repetitions

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3.5 Five Digits Repetitions

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Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to T.J. Eckman, Georgia, USA (email: jeek@jeek.net) in programming the script to develop this paper.

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